

On the basis of analytical and conductance data the complexes presumably have tetrahedral configuration around the metal ion.

The fungitoxicity of three complexes have been studied against rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* at various concentrations. All the three complexes have shown significant activity against *P. oryzae*, particularly at 400 ppm and 1000 ppm. Compound no. 7 is also found to be active against *H. oryzae* at both the concentrations. So this compound can also be used as a suitable fungicide because of its prominent fungitoxicity.

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Reactions of Metal β -Diketonates-III. Reactions of Bis(Acetylacetonato) Cobalt(II) with Chelating Ligands

K. DEY*, S. K. SEN and J. K. BHAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal

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In continuation of our work on the reactions of metal- β -diketonates^{1,2}, we have done some reactions of bis(acetylacetonato) cobalt(II), $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2$ with different chelating ligands; e.g. ethylenediamine (=EN), orthoaminophenol (=OAP-H), glycine (=GLY-H), anthranilic acid (=AA-H), semicarbazide(=SC-H) and thiosemicarbazide(=TSC-H). This note also includes the reactions of

$\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with the Schiff bases N-phenylsalicylaldimine (=SAN-H), N-(2-hydroxyl)-Phenyl salicylaldimine (=SOAP-H₂) and N,N¹-ethylene bis(Salicylaldimine) (=BSEN-H₂).

Treatment of $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2$ with EN, OAP-H, GLY-H and SAN-H in boiling toluene yielded mixed-ligand chelates of cobalt (II and III) of the types $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{EN})]$, (I); $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{OAP})_2]$ (III); $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{GLY})_2]$ (IV); and $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{SAN}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (VIII) respectively. Aerial oxidation of ethanolic solution of (I) and subsequent treatment with saturated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate yielded a cobalt(III) complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{ACAC})_2(\text{EN})]\text{ClO}_4$, (II). On the other hand, complete exchange of ACAC anion was observed when the title complex was reacted with AA-H and SOAP-H₂ in refluxing ethanol/toluene to yield $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{AA})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{SOAP}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (VII) respectively. However, the reaction (refluxing 20 min under N₂) of $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with BSEN-H₂ in ethanol yielded the well-known complex, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{BSEN})$. As observed previously³ the above reaction, when carried out in excess of air, yielded green crystalline complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{BSEN})(\text{ACAC})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is interesting to note that the reactions of SC-H and TSC-H with $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ yielded complexes of cobalt(II) of the types $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ASC}-\text{H})_2$ (VI) and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{ATSC}-\text{H})_2$ (V) respectively (where, ASC-H₂=semicarbazone of acetylacetone and ATSC-H₂=thiosemicarbazone of acetylacetone). Similar observations have been made when $\text{Ni}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Cu}(\text{ACAC})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reacts with above two carbazides and the mechanism for the condensation of C=O group with the -NH₂ group to form -C=N group may be explained as discussed previously^{1,2,4}.

The elemental analyses (Table 1) support the formulations of the present cobalt(II and III) chelates. The diamagnetic nature of the compounds (II), (III) and (IV) (Table 1) support the presence of trivalent cobalt in these chelates; while the paramagnetic nature of the rest of the complexes (Table 1) suggest the presence of bivalent cobalt in these chelates.

The observed magnetic moment value of 4.45 B.M. (Table 1) for $\text{Co}(\text{ATSC}-\text{H})_2$ (V) suggests a tetrahedral geometry^{5,6} for the complex. On the other hand, the μ_{eff} values for $\text{Co}(\text{ASC}-\text{H})_2$ (VI) and $\text{Co}(\text{ACAC})(\text{SAN}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (VIII) are found to be 4.90 B.M. and 4.99 B.M. respectively, which are suggestive of an octahedral structure for each of these complexes. The complexes $\text{Co}(\text{BSEN})$, (IX) ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.24$ B.M.) and $\text{Co}(\text{SOAP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, (VII) ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.45$ B.M.) are square planar.

The electronic spectral data of some of these complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. Based on magnetic and spectral data,

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, COLOUR AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF COBALT(II AND III) COMPLEXES

Complex	Calc. %				Found %				μ_{eff} (B.M.) Room Temp.
	O	H	N	Co	O	H	N	Co	
[Co ^{II} (ACAC) ₂ (EN)], (I) (Light Pink)	45.32	9.98	8.83	18.61	45.28	9.52	8.53	18.21	4.9
[Co ^{III} (ACAC) ₂ (EN)] ClO ₄ , (II) (Brown)	34.58	5.28	6.72	14.17	35.11	5.00	6.05	14.17	Diamagnetic
[Co ^{III} (ACAC)(OAP) ₂], (III) (Red)	54.54	5.08	7.48	15.78	55.01	5.28	7.09	15.93	„
[Co ^{III} (ACAC)(GLY) ₂], (IV) (Brown)	—	—	9.15	19.29	—	—	8.73	18.81	„
[Co ^{II} (ATSC-H) ₂], (V) (Greenish blue)	35.74	4.96	20.84	14.64	36.00	4.85	20.48	14.17	4.45
[Co ^{II} (ASC-H) ₂], (VI) (Light Violet)	38.82	5.99	22.64	15.91	39.20	5.40	22.43	15.83	4.90
[Co ^{II} (SOAP)(H ₂ O)], (VII) (Yellowish brown)	—	—	4.86	20.48	—	—	4.73	20.56	2.45
Co ^{II} (ACAC)(SAN)2H ₂ O, (VIII) (Light Pink)	55.39	5.98	3.58	15.13	55.83	4.89	3.47	15.09	4.99
Co ^{II} (BSEN), (IX) (Red)	—	—	8.61	18.16	—	—	8.56	18.20	2.24

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF SOME COBALT(II AND III) CHELATES AND THEIR TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

Complex	Solvent	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹ (log ϵ)	Probable assignments
[Co ^{II} (ACAC) ₂ (EN)], (I)	EtOH	20,000 (1.85) 19,200 (sh) 15,200 (sh) 7240-6909 (Calcd.)	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)(ν_2) in O _h ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g} (ν_2) in O _h ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (ν_1) in O _h
[Co ^{III} (ACAC)(EN)] ClO ₄ , (II)	H ₂ O	40,000 (sh) 35,000 (sh) 31,000 (3.8) 2,500 (sh) 18,500 (2.2)	⁶ L → e _g π → e _g t _{1g} → π ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g}
[Co ^{II} (ACAC)(OAP) ₂], (III)	EtOH	21,740-17,860 ^a (very broad band) 15,260 (sh)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} (Split components)
[Co ^{III} (ACAC)(GLY) ₂], (IV)	EtOH	21,410 (sh ^a) 15,400 (sh)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} („)
[Co ^{II} (ATSC-H) ₂], (V)	EtOH	43,480 (4.27) 87,740 (4.57) 17,090 (sh) 16,400 (2.60)	Charge transfer ¹ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (ν_2) in T _d
[Co ^{II} (ACAC)(SAN)2H ₂ O, (VIII)	CHCl ₃	20,410 (1.1) 19,500 (1.3) 15,500 (sh) 7380-7045 (Calcd.)	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)(ν_2) in O _h ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g} (ν_1) in O _h ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (ν_1) in O _h

(a) = Not measured above 22,000 cm⁻¹.

(b) = Calculated considering, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.1-2.2$ cf. reference No. 9 p. 319

a pseudooctahedral geometry may be proposed for the complexes Co^{II}(ACAC)₂(EN), (I) and Co^{II}(ACAC)(SAN)₂H₂O (VIII)^{7,8}. While an essentially tetrahedral structure¹¹⁻¹⁴ may be proposed for the blue complex Co^{II}(ATSC-H)₂, (V), although the actual symmetry may be lower than T_d. A very intense band around 17,000 cm⁻¹ observed in the complex may be assigned as due to

4_{1g} → 4_{T₁}(P)(ν_2 in T_d). The ν_2 band could not be detected. The spectral bands, observed for the present cobalt(III) complexes, may be interpreted as done previously¹⁵⁻¹⁸ on the basis of a pseudooctahedral structure. The vibrational spectra of some of these complexes have been obtained. Assignments of the bands of oxygen-bonded chelating acetylacetonate ligand have been made with

reference to a recent assignment of the vibrational bands in tris-(acetylacetonato) cobalt(III) based on a normal coordinate analysis^{1,2}. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ band observed in the range 1580-1540 cm^{-1} , while $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ band observed at about 1530-1510 cm^{-1} range. The bands observed in the range 3350-2950 cm^{-1} for the complexes (I) to (IV) may be assigned as due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ vibrations. Ionic ClO_4^- absorbs at 1180-1100 cm^{-1} in the complex (II). Antisymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of COO^- observed at 1605 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} respectively in the complex (IV).

Experimental details are the same as described previously¹⁻⁴.

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Reduction of Br(V) with Mn(II), Ce(III), [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ and [Ru(dipy)₃]²⁺

C. M. SINGH*, H. C. MISHRA, R. N. UPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University,
Ranchi-834 008 (India)

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MANGANESE(II), cerium(III), tris 1, 10-phenanthroline iron(II) and 2,2'-dipyridyl ruthenium(II) are known¹⁻³ to act as catalysts in Belousov's oscillating reaction (metal ion catalysed reaction between acid bromate and citric acid or its substitute) in which metal ion species oscillate between their reduced and oxidised form and Br(V) is reduced by these reduced form of the metal ions. Since there is no sufficient and systematic report on the reduction of Br(V) with these reductants, in continuation of our studies^{4,5} on Belousov's reaction, we are reporting here our findings on the reduction of Br(V) with Mn(II), Ce(III), [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ and [Ru(dipy)₃]²⁺ in aqueous 3*N* H₂SO₄ acidic medium.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of extra purity. 1, 10-phenanthroline iron(II) and 2,2'-dipyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes were prepared following the methods reported earlier^{6,7}.

Potentiometric titrations were done by a modified method^{8,9}. 10 ml of M/60 solution of KBrO₃ was delivered to a number of reaction vessels and then M/10 solution of the reductants were delivered to each reaction vessel in increasing order and potentiometric readings were recorded after the storage of the reaction mixture at different time intervals during which reaction mixture attains equilibrium. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (25°).

Results and Discussion

In case of reduction of Br(V) with manganese(II), sharp inflexions were observed at 1.8, 3.4 and 6.7 ml corresponding to 1st, 2nd and 4th electron reduction stages of Br(V) which is suggestive of the formation of BrO₂, HBrO₂ and HBr respectively at those stages. A very sharp inflexion at 6.7 ml corresponds to 4th electron reduction stage of Br(V), i.e., formation of hypobromous acid which was confirmed and titrated with arsenite. The

* To whom correspondence should be made.